

First record of *Eriovixia excelsa* (Simon, 1889) from South Africa (Araneae: Araneidae)

A.S. Dippenaar-Schoeman^{1,2}, C.R. Haddad³, J. van Zyl⁴ & P. Webb⁵

¹ ARC – Plant Health and Protection, Private Bag X134, Queenswood 0121, South Africa; DippenaarA@arc.agric.za

² Department of Zoology, University of Venda, South Africa

³ Department of Zoology and Entomology, University of the Free State, South Africa

⁴ Jordaanpark, Heidelberg, Gauteng, South Africa

⁵ SANSa team member, Irene, Gauteng, South Africa

ABSTRACT

We present the first records of the spider *Eriovixia excelsa* (Simon, 1889) from South Africa. The general morphology of live specimens is discussed and photographs of both sexes are provided, with notes on their behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Eriovixia* Archer, 1951 is a small genus known from 22 species and exhibits a wide geographical distribution from Africa to Southeast Asia. Three species are known from Africa and the rest from Asia (World Spider Catalogue 2021). The type species *Eriovixia rhinura* (Pocock, 1900) was described from Western and Central Africa, *E. napiformis* (Thorell, 1899) from East Africa and Yemen, and *E. turbinata* (Thorell, 1899) from Central Africa.

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) a large number of specimens from several localities in South Africa (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015) were sampled, many of them members of the family Araneidae. Several specimens sampled from orb-webs had a distinct subtriangular abdomen and a short caudal appendage. Features of the species were compared with illustrations and the original description of *Eriovixia excelsa* (Simon, 1889). This is a species with a wide distribution range known from several countries, but is recorded from South Africa for the first time here.

METHODS

Though the SANSa Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2012) photographs of the species provided additional information on their morphology, distribution and behaviour. Voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria (NCA).

TAXONOMY

Eriovixia excelsa (Simon, 1889)

Figures 1-12

Glyptogona excelsa Simon, 1889: 337.

Eriovixia excelsa Grasshoff, 1986: 118; Barrion & Litsinger, 1995: 643.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: It has a worldwide distribution and is known from India, Pakistan, China, Taiwan, Philippines and Indonesia. New records are presented here from South Africa.

MATERIAL EXAMINED IN SOUTH AFRICA

The species was sampled by hand or with a sweep net in South Africa from the Savanna and Grassland biomes. It was sampled from the following localities (Fig. 12): **Gauteng:** Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.80, 28.77), 1f (NCA 2014/3458); Irene, Gem Village Field (-25.87, 28.22), 1f, 1m (NCA 2016/3902); Roodeplaat Research Station (-25.66, 28.35), 1f (NCA 2014/3792); Hammanskraal, 1f (NCA 2017/1801); Heidelberg (-26.50, 28.36) [photo]. **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24), 1f (NCA 2019/201); Pinetown (-29.81, 30.85). **Limpopo:** Bela-Bela, Klein Kariba, 1f (NCA 2016/3708); Buzzard Mountain (-25.84, 28.28) [photo]; Kampersrust (-24.48, 30.83) [photo]; Lephale/Ellisras (-23.67, 27.71) [photo]. **Mpumalanga:** Kampersrus (-24.48, 30.83) [photo]; Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23), 1f (NCA 2014/3546); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96), 1f (NCA 2013/1821). **North West:** Mooiooi (-25.75, 27.56), 1f (NCA 2014/3546)

MORPHOLOGY

Description: Female: TL 4.7-5 mm. Carapace slightly longer than wide; anteriorly narrowed (Fig. 1); pilose, bearing short thick setae (Fig. 11), covered with white pubescence, especially in elevated cephalic area (Fig. 2); anterior eye row recurved, posterior eye row almost straight; anterior median eyes smaller than posterior median eyes; lateral eyes situated close together on small tubercles (Fig. 4). Sternum heart-shaped, pointed posteriorly; covered with white pubescence (Fig. 5). Leg formula: 1243; legs moderately long, thin, clothed with pubescence; femora of all legs dark; patellae and tibiae yellowish dorsally. Abdomen slightly wider than long; subtriangular with caudal appendage above and beyond spinnerets (Fig. 3); mottled grey; dorsum decorated with chalk white folium but not very distinct in many specimens; four rows of small white spots (Fig. 6); venter black with two yellow spots between spinnerets and epigyne (Fig. 5). Epigynum with short broad scape (Fig. 10). Male: a little smaller than female. Carapace shiny dark brown, with cluster of setae directed forward between eyes (Figs 7-8). Abdomen dorsum darker than female, with the four rows of white spots more prominent; dark ventrally, with two yellow spots (Fig. 9).

Figures 1-12 *Eriovixia excelsa* female (1-6, 10, 11) and male (7-9). 1-2, 7-8. Dorsal view; 3. Lateral view, showing hump; 4. Eye pattern, anterior view; 5, 9. Ventral view; 6. Female at night in orb-web; 10. Epigyne; 11. Carapace integument; 12. South African records of *Eriovixia excelsa* (Photo credits: P. Webb).

BEHAVIOUR

Eriovixia excelsa is a nocturnal orb-weaver. They spin typical geometric orb-webs between vegetation (Fig. 6), usually with a very long bridge line. On two occasions they were found to rest 1.8 to 1.9 meters above the ground on the northern side of the plants during the day. They take up a position on top of a leaf, not hiding below. Faint silk thread could be seen below the spider (Figs 13-16).

This is possibly another bird dropping mimic. The egg sac is also deposited on the leaf (Figs 17-18). Heron (2016) observed a mimetic relationship between the beetle *Cassida calvaria* and *E. excelsa* in the Palmiet Nature Reserve at Westville near Durban in October 2010. They were of similar size, colouring and body patterns (Heron 2016).

Figures 13-18 *Eriovixia excelsa*. 13-16. Female on leaf; 17. Female with egg sac; 18. Female with remnants of egg sac after spiderlings had hatched (Photo credits: J. van Zyl).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was made possible by the financial support from Agricultural Research Council (ARC) and the National Research Foundation of South Africa.

REFERENCES

- BARRION, A.T. & LITSINGER, J.A.** 1995. *Riceland spiders of South and Southeast Asia*. CAB International, Wallingford, UK, xix + 700 pp.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., HADDAD, C.R., FOORD, S.H., LYLE, R., LOTZ, L.N. & MARAIS, P.** 2015. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa): Review of current knowledge, constraints and future needs for documenting spider diversity (Arachnida: Araneae). *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Africa* **70**: 245–275.
- DIPPENAAR-SCHOEMAN, A.S., LYLE, R. & VAN DEN BERG, A.M.** 2012. Bioinformatics on the spiders of South Africa. *Serket* **13**: 121–127.
- GRASSHOFF, M.** 1986. Die Radnetzspinnen-Gattung *Neoscona* in Afrika (Arachnida: Araneae). *Annalen Zoologische Wetenschappen* **250**: 1–123.
- HERON, H.** 2016. Possible mimetic relationships between South African spiders and tortoise beetles (Chrysomelidae, Cassidinae). *SANSa News* **26**: 9-10.
- SIMON, E.** 1889. Arachnides de l'Himalaya, recueillis par MM. Oldham et Wood-Mason, et faisant partie des collections de l'Indian Museum. Première partie. *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bengal* **58**: 334–344.
- WORLD SPIDER CATALOG** 2021. World Spider Catalog. Version 22.0. Natural History Museum Bern, online at <http://wsc.nmbe.ch>, accessed on 15 February 2021.